

MAPPING THE GLOBAL GENDER WAGE GAP: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW OF REGIONAL DETERMINANTS AND METHODOLOGIES

Abstract.

This systematic literature review provides a comprehensive examination of the gender wage gap across various global regions, analysing key determinants, policy interventions, and applied methodologies to study the gender wage gap. The study encompasses developed, developing, and transition economies, with a specific focus on Europe, Asia, North America, South America, the former Soviet Union, and Africa. The authors combined findings from 73 empirical articles selected from an initial pool of 1,267 references. The findings highlight that while developed economies have made progress in reducing wage disparities, developing and transition economies continue to struggle with structural labor market inequalities and weak enforcement of policies. Future research should focus on region-specific interventions to achieve sustainable progress in closing the gender wage gap.

Key words: Gender wage gap, wage inequality, regional wage differences, systematic literature review.

Introduction

The gender wage gap is one of the most significant challenges worldwide. It is caused by cost, cultural, and systemic issues. Although some policies and laws have been put in place to eliminate gender bias, women are still being paid less than men in most sectors of the economy, at all levels of education and in most geographic regions. Anjum (2016) points out that this gap not only affects the financial well-being of the women and their households but also has implications for economic development, social justice and asset creation [1]. Rusi (2019) also postulate that women are still faced with barriers to career progression, which include discrimination in hiring and promotion, exclusion from leadership positions and low participation in high-paying occupations [2]. Sugiharti and Kurnia (2018) also note that the unequal burden of care work limits women's ability to work full-time, thereby increasing the gender wage gap [3].

The causes of the gender pay gap have been discussed for a long time. For instance, scholars have argued that the gap is primarily driven by labor market discrimination; however, others have identified work experience, occupational segregation, industry choices, and negotiation behaviors as the primary causes [4; 5]. According to Kumar (2013), women still dominate low-paid professions, such as education, healthcare, and retail, while men dominate high-paid industries, including technology, finance, and engineering [6]. Moreover, Mohanty (2021) argued that gender-based occupational segregation and societal norms regarding career choices still prevail, which in turn leads to a structural wage gap [7].

Solving the gender pay gap needs to take place on several fronts, including through measures such as pay transparency, parental leave, and gender-sensitive education initiatives. Although antidiscrimination laws and labor market regulations have been partially successful, their efficacy varies by region and labour market structure, especially in transition economies [8].

This study adopts a structured approach to analysing gender wage inequality through a systematic review methodology. It examines key theoretical perspectives, measurement techniques, and empirical evidence from recent research, focusing on three core areas: (i) key determinants of the gender wage gap, (ii) regional variations in wage inequality, and (iii) policy responses and their effectiveness. The review synthesises findings from peer-reviewed journal articles, policy reports, and empirical studies, ensuring methodological rigor and broad geographic coverage.

Although numerous studies have examined the gender wage gap in specific economic contexts, a systematic review of the literature across multiple regions remains lacking. The only previous effort to conduct a similar review is the study by Dorjnyambuu (2024), which focuses on income inequality in Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries [9]. However, that study is limited to one regional context and does not encompass the wider global spectrum of gender-based wage inequality. This limitation is particularly important because recent empirical studies from Central Asia by Kovaleva & Taylor (2023); Kovaleva et al., (2025) indicate that household structure, patrilocal living arrangements, and gender norms may substantially influence women’s labour allocation, earnings, and innovative activity, yet such institutional mechanisms remain weakly represented in the broader international literature [10;11]. This research addresses that gap by presenting a systematic review of the gender wage gap across different economic contexts and by comparing developed, developing, and transition economies.

By integrating insights from diverse economic contexts, this research seeks to provide a nuanced understanding of the structural and policy-driven factors that influence gender wage disparities. The findings underscore the need for targeted, region-specific interventions that address both structural inequalities and policy enforcement challenges. Future research should continue to explore innovative policy solutions and interdisciplinary approaches to effectively close the gender wage gap.

Methodology

This paper aims to investigate the gender wage gap through a systematic literature review (SLR) of prior empirical research across various regions, including Europe, Asia, South America, North America, the USSR, and Africa. The methodology involves a wide-ranging literature review of key theoretical frameworks, statistical techniques, and regional studies to understand the causes and patterns of the wage gap between men and women. The SLR was conducted in three stages to ensure transparency and replicability: planning, literature search, and reporting. And has been carried out systematically in several stages (Table 1):

1. The first stage was the **planning stage**, which entailed a scoping database search. Key search terms were determined, relevant sources were identified, and inclusion/exclusion criteria were defined.
2. The literature search stage involved screening and selecting studies based on titles and abstracts that met the inclusion criteria, resulting in a list of potential studies.
3. Then, a **critical appraisal** is conducted to assess these studies against the research questions, and the selection is further restricted to the final list of studies for synthesis.
4. Furthermore, **network analysis** was applied to identify co-occurrence patterns and relationships between studies, ensuring that all areas of the literature on the gender wage gap are systematically covered.

Stages	Reference status	Number of references
1. Identification	Initial entire references	1267
	Duplicates	-217
	Unrelated references	-578
	Number of references after cleaning	472
2. Screening	Excluded references that do not meet the inclusion criteria	-317
	Number of references for eligibility	155
3. Eligibility	Excluded references by critical appraisal	-82
	Number of references for synthesis (final sample)	73

Source. Authors' estimations based on SLR analysis

Table 1. Data selection process

that the study includes peer-reviewed journal articles and empirical studies on gender wage gaps across various economies, sourced from Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. To ensure the relevance and recency of sources, all article abstracts were first examined, and 155 of

the most recent and thematically most relevant studies were further reviewed. After a thorough review of the methodology, scope, and findings, 73 articles were included in the current review. Sources were selected for their methodological rigour, geographic scope, and relevance to key research themes, including gender wage gap techniques, labour market dynamics, and policy interventions (Table 1).

Findings

1. Wage Inequality Around the World

In his seminal study, Blinder (1973), using the 1967 PSID, analysed the female-male wage differential among whites in the US. He finds that the single most significant cause of the differential for the women in the same educational and occupational category is the failure of women's wages to rise over their working lives. In addition, although men and women differ slightly in their educational endowments, men report significantly higher wage increments for advancing to higher academic levels.

According to Chinara (2018), depending on the period and area of examination, studies have revealed that these disparities are either growing or shrinking, changing to varied degrees, and evolving by varying magnitudes. The Global Gender Gap Report from the World Economic Forum reveals slow progress in reducing gender differences on several fronts. According to the survey, although the gender gap has closed slightly since 2006, it has narrowed by only 4%. If this trend were to continue, it would take more than a century for women worldwide to catch up to men [12].

According to Poddar and Mukhopadhyay (2019), gender wage inequality is a chronic socioeconomic malaise in both developed and developing countries [13]. At the same time, Ognjenović (2021) argue that this problem is more pronounced in developing countries. Although many countries today have minimum wage legislation and regulations that require equal treatment of men and women at work, gender wage disparity persists as a global labor market characteristic. The overall gender gap has narrowed, but the pay gaps have widened, and it will take 257 more years, i.e., by the year 2257, for pay equity to be established [14].

Given its multifaceted structure and the various scenarios in terms of economic, social, and cultural aspects, measuring and comparing female labor market conditions and the gender wage gap across nations is a challenging undertaking. But still, in their scientific writings, economists from all around the world frequently discuss the topic of gender-based professional discrimination. The national level is another forum where this issue is discussed. The problem persists, however.

Despite government efforts to close the gender pay gap in budgeted and state-owned businesses, as well as women's competitiveness in the job market, access to better education, and higher productivity, the gender pay gap remains unfavourable to women. According to Avduyevskaia & Kuporov (2018), this issue is not only of national significance, where it manifests itself in the undervaluation of the financial compensation for women's labor, but also on a more local level, within the context of private organisations: An employer whose prejudices are placed above the interests of the company and those associated with maximising profits incurs enormous losses by hiring men who are less productive than women [15].

To conclude, the authors observe that, in general, developed countries have smaller gender wage gaps than developing countries. For example, in North America, the gender wage gap is relatively small compared to other regions. The World Economic Forum data indicate that the United States has a gender wage gap of approximately 80%, while Canada has a gap of about 87%. In Europe, the gender wage gap is also quite wide. The gender wage gap in the EU is approximately 16%, according to Eurostat, the European Union's statistical agency. However, the gap is much higher in some countries, for example, Estonia (22%), Czech Republic (20%), and Romania (19), and lower in others, for example, Slovenia (5%), Italy (9%), and Belgium (11%). In Asia, the gender wage gap is typically higher than in North America and Europe. The gender wage gap in China is about 20%, while in India, it is 34%, according to the International Labour Organization. In Africa, the gender wage gap is also usually higher than in North America and Europe. The gender wage gap in Africa is about 37%, according to the African Development Bank. A wide

variation in the gender wage gap also characterises Latin America. The gender wage gap in Latin America is about 17%, according to the International Labour Organization. However, the gap is much worse in some countries, such as Honduras (25%), Guatemala (24%), and Venezuela (22%), while it is better in others, including Chile (8%), Argentina (10%), and Costa Rica (11%).

2. Europe

According to Staboulis (2017), the gender wage gap is a sociopolitical issue that affects Europe and serves as a barrier to social integrity, cohesion, and the solidarity economy. Since 1970, efforts have been made at the national level to define and eliminate the gender wage gap. Although the pay gap phenomenon has decreased, it remains higher than the average for Europe [16].

Fad'os & Bohdalova (2019) state that, although the European Commission is committed to reducing gender disparity, it still exists in the workplace. Even though the Europe 2020 employment strategy, as well as the strategy for equality between women and men, supports gender equality, which the Charter requires of Fundamental Rights. However, in contrast to men, women still have a weaker position in the job market [17].

Boll & Lagemann (2019) and Castellano & Rocca (2014) also concur that in the majority of European nations, income disparities between men and women have a long-standing history [18; 19]. Boll & Lagemann (2019) examined the causes of the wage gap between men and women in 26 European countries and found that the gender wage gap across nations was 14.2% in 2014. However, results at the country level are quite different, with Estonia and Germany exhibiting significant differences of more than 20%, while Belgium, Luxembourg, Slovenia, and Romania show small gaps of less than 5% [19]. While Castellano & Rocca's (2014) results indicate that Ireland and Scandinavian nations have the best working conditions for women, several countries in Eastern and Southern Europe rank poorly [19].

In addition, Fad'os and Bohdalova (2019) analysed gender disparities in employment across 28 EU countries from 2000 to 2017. The highest gender inequality value was reported in southern countries, such as Malta, Italy, and Greece, while the lowest value was reported in northern countries, including Sweden and Finland [19].

Finally, J. Landmesser (2019) utilised data from EU-SILC (Statistics on Income and Living Conditions) and confirmed that the size of the gender wage gap varies significantly among the members of the European Union. Europe can be divided into two main categories: those where the majority of reported income disparities cannot be explained by observed features and those where both the explained and unexplained impacts are positive, with the explained effect being significantly more significant for lower income ranges [20].

According to Anić & Krstić (2019), the Serbian labor market continues to have significant gender disparities [21]. Majchrowska et al. (2014) also state that women in Poland typically earn less than males do despite having higher qualifications, which indicates that there is gender discrimination in the workplace [22]. At the same time, Petreski et al. (2014) suggest that for highly educated women in Macedonia, there is no gender wage discrimination, with a range of 5.4 to 9.8% [23].

Finally, Hedija & Musil (2020) research focuses on differences in remuneration between men and women in the Baltic states. There is an 11 percent gender pay gap in Latvia and Lithuania, which is probably a form of wage discrimination against women. The gender gap in Estonia is significantly higher, standing at approximately 21% [24].

To sum up, according to the literature review analysis, the gender wage gap is also a persistent issue in the European Union, with women earning on average 16% less than men. However, the gap varies widely across countries, with some countries such as Slovenia (5%), Italy (9%), and Belgium (11%) having a smaller gap, and others such as Estonia (22%), Czech Republic (20%), and Romania (19%) having a more significant gap. Factors such as occupation, education and experience are the main drivers of the gender wage gap in the EU.

Furthermore, women are underrepresented in higher-paying sectors, such as STEM fields, and overrepresented in lower-paying sectors, including healthcare and education. Moreover, the gender pay gap is also connected with the gender pensions gap, where women tend to have smaller pensions than men at retirement because of working fewer years and earning less over their lifetime.

Different policies have been implemented by policymakers to address this issue, including advocating for equal pay, promoting women's participation in the labor market, and enhancing the accessibility and affordability of childcare and eldercare. However, there is a need to ensure that these policies are effectively enforced and that the gender wage gap in Europe is addressed and closed.

3. Asia

Several researchers have also identified gender wage inequalities in Southeast Asia countries. For example, Bui and Permpoonwiwat (2015) established that in Malaysia's labour market, discrimination still holds a significant amount of weight and has an evident effect on gender wage gaps [25]. Sukma and Kadir (2019) employed data from the 2016 Indonesia National Labor Force Survey and revealed that women are paid approximately 30 percent less than men [26]. According to Ismail, Park and Ratha (2015) and Paez and Tin (2021), gender-based discrimination is also another unmeasured burden in Myanmar's labor market [27;28].

Yusuf et al. (2021) concur with their findings and note that the Myanmar government has made several attempts to promote gender equality in the economy. Yet, discrimination against women still exists in the workplace [29].

A similar situation can be observed in South Asian countries such as India, Nepal, and Bangladesh. According to Ognjenović (2021), India exhibits the highest level of salary discrimination between the sexes among BRIC countries. The World Economic Forum (WEF) has conducted a survey that highlights India's issue, ranking it among the top 10 nations in the world for women's economic participation. India is ranked 112th out of 153 countries examined in the Global Gender Gap Report 2020, with an index value of 0.068 [30]. Ara (2021) also states that in nearly all industries and professions in India, women's pay is much lower than men's [31]. At the same time, Chinara (2018) found that "India has tightened its gender gap by 2% in a year, which now stands at 68% across the four pillars of economy, education, health and political representation" [12]. Varkkey et al. (2017) confirm the results of other researchers about India and argue that even though the Indian government has made numerous steps to combat discrimination against female employees, India still maintains a sizable gender wage disparity [32].

Yamamoto et al. (2019) analysed the gender wage gap in Nepal using data representing over 6,000 workers from the Nepal Living Standard Survey. They found that the gender pay gap is highly crucial in Nepal, where significant differences exist between men and women in educational attainment levels [33]. Ahmed and McGillivray (2015) also investigated changes in the gender wage gap in Bangladesh from 1999 to 2009. They observed that the gap in average wages between men and women decreased by 31% over this period [34]. Ahmed & Maitra (2018) empirically investigated the gender wage gap in Bangladesh during the period 2005–2009 and demonstrated that women are still paid less than men [35].

The authors also analysed what is happening in Western Asian countries, using Iran and Turkey as examples. According to Mirsardoo et al. (2011), a study from different regions of Iran suggests that pervasive and institutionalised inequalities exist within households. Iran was ranked 82nd out of 124 nations in terms of reducing gender inequality in 2004 and 118 out of 124 in 2007. In comparison to the economy and wealth, there is less gender inequality in health and education. In 2005, 15.4 percent of women were working, but by 2008, that number had increased to 18.5 percent. When comparing men and women with academic backgrounds, the unemployment rate for women fell from 23.6 percent in 2005 to 9.3 percent in 2008 [36]. Kaya & Selim (2018) utilised the 2015 TURKSTAT household labor force survey and identified a substantial relationship between human capital indicators and monthly pay. Moreover, they observed significant

disparities in pay among regions, genders, and occupations. Although women's human capital is superior to men's, salary inequality persists [37].

One of the best examples of an East Asian country is China. According to Heshmati & Su (2017), although women have higher levels of educational attainment on average, they receive lower wages than men. Both facts suggest a potential discrimination against women in China [38]. Another researcher, Xiu & Gunderson (2013), utilised the Life Histories and Social Change in Contemporary China (LHSCCC) data to present fresh evidence of Chinese salary disparities between men and women. They found that, before accounting for the impact of various pay-determining factors, women are paid approximately 75 percent less than men in terms of base pay, performance pay, and total compensation [39].

Authors of current literature review analyses conclude that the gender wage gap in Asia continues to be a problem, and it affects the lives of women in the region. Research shows that women in Asia earn lower salaries than men in similar positions, and the gap is 10% in countries like China and Japan and over 30% in South Korea and India. These differences can be attributed to several factors, including discrimination, restricted education and job opportunities and cultural norms that prevent women from participating in the workforce. Although some advancement has been made in the last few years, for example, through the implementation of policies aimed at improving workplace gender balance, the gender wage gap in Asia remains a significant challenge that needs further attention

4. South and North America

Authors of this literature review analysis have also observed that several researchers across South American countries have researched gender wage discrimination. For example, as reported by Morello & Anjolim (2021), the discriminatory component was found to be significant across all recent years in Brazil [40].

Similar results are also found in Bolivia, Trinidad, and Ecuador. For example, Urquidi et al. (2021) state that women in Bolivia are disproportionately employed in low-paying jobs and receive lower pay for similar labor than men. However, authors also found solid evidence that the gender pay gap narrowed significantly over the 25 years from 1993 to 2018 [41]. Another study from Trinidad and Tobago, conducted by Mahabir and Ramrattan (2015), also confirmed the existence of gender wage discrimination. According to the article, the demographics with the highest levels of [42] are those in the age category of 35 to 44, with an income range of \$3,000 to \$5,999, and employed in the private versus public sectors. Albuja-Echeverría & Enríquez-Rodríguez (2018) also found that in Ecuador, there is a statistically significant net pay differential of 4.5%, favoring men over women, and salary discrimination based on sex accounts for 66% of this disparity [43].

Another group of researchers studied the gender wage gap in North American countries. According to Collins (2017), full-time working women in Mississippi earn approximately 27% less than full-time working men, and the existing 18% pay disparity may have some discriminatory components [44]. Gharehgozli and Atal (2020) contend that over three decades, there has been a modest decline in the total gender wage difference in the USA, which was 53 percent in 1986 and 67 percent in 2016 [45]. According to Utami (2015), cultural norms about gender roles in the US workplace had an impact on hiring and retention decisions, which led to additional gender-discriminatory behaviors (generally) and gender wage discrimination [46].

While Peticar and Tejada (2022) determined how taste-based prejudice affected the labor market outcomes in nine Latin American countries. They discover that prejudice is the only factor that consistently has an effect on women and contributes significantly to the explanation of gender wage discrepancies. Furthermore, prejudice has significant detrimental consequences on gender inequalities in participation, employment/unemployment, and rates of self-employment [47].

Popli (2013) tried to analyse the gender wage gap between men and women in Mexico over the last two decades. He discovered proof of gender discrimination in the job market and argues that the average level of prejudice significantly decreased before beginning to rise once more. The distribution of discrimination also evolved. With little to no change at the upper tail of the wage

distribution, the estimated discrimination at the lower tail of the wage distribution has decreased over time on average [48]. While, Mendoza González's (2020) findings support the sticky-floor hypothesis in Mexico, which states that at low-income levels, male workers earn more per hour than female workers. However, disparities narrow and sometimes even reverse, favoring women over men at the highest income levels [49].

To conclude, the gender wage gap in South America is still an issue that prevents women's economic empowerment and affects their quality of life. Despite these improvements, women in the region still receive lower pay than men for the same job. The gap results from discrimination and bias in the labor market, restricted access to education and job opportunities for women, and the gender stereotypes that prevent women from working in some areas. The efforts to decrease the gender wage gap in South America include implementing policies for equal pay and non-discrimination, improving access to education and job training for women, and increasing awareness of the issue through education and public campaigns.

A similar situation exists in North American countries, where women earn less than men in various industries and occupations. In the United States, for example, the national gender wage gap currently stands at around 80 cents to a man's dollar. Canada's gender wage gap is also present, although it is slightly smaller than the US, with women earning around 87 cents to a man's dollar. The gap is further explained by discrimination, gender segregation in occupations and the absence of family-friendly policies. Despite the efforts made to close the gap through measures such as equal pay laws and diversity management, the gap still persists, indicating that more attention needs to be paid to this issue to achieve gender equality in North American countries.

5. USSR

The wage gap received by the working population also remains one of the most significant social and economic problems in Russia. As Avduyevskaia & Kuporov (2018) pointed out, this issue is driven by both macroeconomic and microeconomic factors [15]. Panov (2014) found in his study that, although women receive less money than men, they are still more favorable from a socioeconomic point of view and have higher levels of education and better health. Furthermore, as Panov (2014) notes, the leading causes of gender wage differences besides horizontal segregation and the traditional division of industries into male and female are social prejudice and gender roles for women. Overall, due to the conflict between normative-legal acts requiring gender equality in all sectors of life and discriminatory social views, the topic of addressing gender discrimination in contemporary Russian society has become more urgent [50].

The situation in Belarus and Ukraine is very similar. According to Tsymbaliuk & Volkovska (2021), despite Ukraine's commitments to preventing discrimination and promoting gender equality, the issue of gender wage discrepancies remains a concern [51]. In addition, Kulak (2019) argues that gender segregation in the labour market in Belarus remains an issue, despite the law guaranteeing the right to work and equal pay for men and women. Social variables, rather than biological differences, are the primary causes of inequalities between men and women in Belarus, as evidenced by objective statistics, including cultural norms and rates of change, social conventions, and other factors [52].

To sum up, the gender wage gap in the Soviet Union (USSR) was one of the existing gaps throughout the history of the socialist state. The Communist Party of the USSR, for one moment, was vocal on the issue of gender equality and women's participation in the workforce. Still, women in the USSR typically received lower pay for the same work as men. The gap was linked to hiring and promotion discrimination, absence of education and training, and cultural perception of women's work. Furthermore, the Soviet system of job classification, which allocated almost every job into different categories according to the level of skills and salary, often marked many jobs typically done by women as low-paying. Even in the presence of efforts like quotas for women in leadership positions and affirmative action, the gender wage gap was still a significant issue in the Soviet Union.

6. Africa

Bhorat & Goga (2013) examined the pay of women in South Africa and established that a pay gap exists, with the disparity being worse at the lower end of the pay scale than at the top [53]. Bosch & Barit (2020) also supported this finding and stated that gender pay gap is still one of the most significant barriers between men and women in South Africa [54]. However, as Karshenas et al. (2016) noted, Middle East and North Africa (MENA) countries have made improvements in the education of women and the reduction of birth rates; yet, most women in the region are not employed, and those who are working face numerous issues related to their gender. Therefore, for countries in the area, having a low proportion of women in the workforce is costly, which hampers their economic development and growth [55].

Nkoumou Ngoa & Lemven Wirba's (2021) study results demonstrate that men in Uganda continue to earn more money than women. Human capital variables continue to have a significant mitigating influence through returns to endowments (discrimination), despite the activities and strategies implemented in Uganda to eliminate the gender gap in education and training nationwide [56]. Biltagy's (2019) paper focuses on calculating the salary gaps between men and women in Egypt to understand the causes of this variation better and control it. A measure of improvement is that the projected salary disparity between men and women in 2006 and 2012 was 25% and 21%, respectively. Females are less likely than males to hold high-level and well-paying positions, which helps explain some of this discrepancy. However, other less obvious factors, such as non-cognitive talents and psychological traits, also contribute to the gender wage gap [57]. Finally, Tandrayen-Ragoobur & Pydayya (2015) investigated the Mauritian labour market and found that there is a combination of both glass ceiling and sticky floor effects. This provides evidence of gender discrimination in the Mauritian labour market [58].

The final section of the current comprehensive literature review focused on the gender pay gap in Africa. As an observer, the gender wage gap here persisted for years. It has implications for the economic status of women and their families and hence is a barrier to gender equality. It has been established that women in Africa earn between 10% and 30% less than men for similar work. The gender pay gap in Africa is driven by discrimination and bias in the workplace, limited access to education and training, and cultural and societal norms that prevent women from entering the labor market. To address the gender pay gap in Africa, a multi-pronged strategy is necessary, encompassing the promotion of equal pay, the education and training of women, and the transformation of societal norms towards women in the workforce.

Results

Theoretical Frameworks and Methodological Techniques

The authors of the current systematic literature review (SLR) conclude that the gender wage gap is one of the most widely discussed issues worldwide. Wage gaps are measured and analysed using various methods across nations.

First of all, the most common method is a comparison of median earnings between genders in a particular occupation; however, this method does not capture other potential explanatory factors of the gender wage gap, such as experience or education. Secondly, researchers apply the regression analysis to control for these additional factors and estimate the unexplained portion of the wage gap [20].

Thirdly, there are well-established methods for examining wage disparity, one of which is the Oaxaca-Blinder (1973) decomposition technique. It is used to understand why earnings differ between groups of workers (men and women) by splitting it into two components. The first is linked to individual traits, such as education and experience. The second reason is that this occurs due to the presence of discrimination and cannot be explained by these characteristics [59;60;61;62].

Additionally, we observe that scientists employ various decomposition techniques to identify the sources of the wage gap. For example, according to Landmesser (2019), numerous new methods for decomposing income inequalities exist that extend beyond the Oaxaca-Blinder

decomposition. With the help of these new methods, it is possible to study differences in income distributions across various population groups and to decompose them at different quantile points [20].

1. Another widely applied technique is the Juhn–Murphy–Pierce (1993) wage decomposition, also known as the JMP method. It helps to examine how wage shifts occur over time. This approach breaks down wage changes into three parts: alterations in the workforce, composition shifts in the value of investing in capital (such as education and experience), and variations in the residual (not easily explained). JMP method can be particularly insightful for studying ethnic wage differences. It is helpful to examine the reasons behind such wage disparities and assess the effectiveness of implemented policies [63].
2. Another widely used decomposition method is the Machado and Mata (2005) decomposition. It provides an approach for analysing shifts in wage distribution over time compared to the JMP decomposition method by offering a comprehensive perspective on how the wage distribution and its influencing factors evolve. The technique breaks down shifts in wage distribution into four components. Changes in the wage level of the distribution, variance adjustments, variations in skewness, and alterations in kurtosis. It helps researchers identify the factors contributing to the wage gap and evaluate the impact of reforms [64].
3. In 2008, Ñopo (2008) proposed a new decomposition method under his name, Ñopo Decomposition. This is a non-parametric alternative to the Oaxaca-Blinder matching approach, which compares individuals with similar observable characteristics across gender groups [65].
4. The following decomposition method was introduced by Firpo, Fortin, and Lemieux (FFL) in 2009. It is used to analyse how wage distribution evolves statistically. This approach builds upon the work of Machado and Mata (2005). The technique breaks down alterations into five components: variations in the wage value, shifts in quantiles, modifications in percentiles, adjustments to the Gini coefficient and changes in density. The decomposition method by Firpo provides a view of the factors influencing shifts in wage distribution by breaking down the distribution into percentile ranges and analysing differences across various parts of the distribution spectrum. [66;67].
5. A bit later, Gelbach Decomposition (2016) was introduced. This method identifies the contribution of omitted variables in regression-based decomposition, enhancing the Oaxaca-Blinder approach [68].
6. The most recent decomposition method involves machine learning. According to various studies initiated in 2020, this method enables researchers to apply machine learning techniques to decomposition analysis, thereby enhancing accuracy and robustness to large datasets. [69;70;71].

In addition, another well-known method to measure the gender wage gap is the Recentered Influence Function (RIF). It is used to estimate how much each data point affects the models' prediction in statistics to identify outliers or essential observations in a dataset analysis context. RIF values are calculated for each data point to see how the models' predictions change when that specific point is removed from consideration [72;73].

Another way to measure the gender wage gap is to use the Difference-in-Differences (DD) method. This is a statistical analysis technique used to determine the effect of an intervention or policy on a group of people. It involves comparing the changes in an outcome variable over time between two groups: one that received the treatment and one that did not, as explained by Bloom in 2012 [73].

Additionally, according to Navarro-Gómez (2015), an Instrumental Variable (IV) is also used to analyse how one variable (known as the treatment or independent variable) influences another variable (referred to as the outcome or dependent variable) when confounding factors are present [74].

Finally, according to Cook (2021), the Heckman model is used for the sample selection. This method is employed to address the issue of sample selection bias in studies. It helps researchers

differentiate between the selection process and the result, allowing them to carry out a two-step estimation process [75].

Authors of current literature review observed that the size of the gender wage gap and the rate of its closure over time differ across countries and nations. Therefore, the methodology for studying the gender wage gap depends on the research question and the availability of data. No single approach is universally accepted as the best, and sometimes, a combination of methods is necessary to provide a more comprehensive view.

Conclusion

The gender wage gap is one of the most enduring global issues, fueled by economic, social, and institutional factors. Despite efforts and some positive changes, significant differences persist between the regions, and women's income remains a key indicator of gender equality. Structural inequalities, occupational segregation, and persistent discrimination in the labour market are the primary explanations for wage inequality.

This review reveals that the gender wage gaps differ significantly across developed, developing, and transitioning economies. The wage gaps are more minor in developed countries; however, in developing economies, cultural beliefs and segregation in the labour market reinforce the wage differences. In transition economies, including those in Central Asia, wage structures are shaped by historical and institutional factors that need deliberate actions.

Effective policy measures include those such as wage transparency, parental leave policies, and anti-discrimination policies. However, enforcement remains a significant issue. In addition, the global and technological factors that contribute to gender wage inequality mean that policymakers must be flexible.

Future studies should also incorporate multidisciplinary analysis of the issue, encompassing economic, social, and behavioral perspectives, to propose specific policies tailored to each context. To maintain equal remuneration between men and women, ongoing efforts are needed from policymakers, employers, and civil society. Thus, the organisation of a sustainable and inclusive labour market, along with strong legal frameworks, will not only help achieve wage equality between women and men but also contribute to economic development.

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КАРТА ГЕНДЕРНОГО РАЗРЫВА В ОПЛАТЕ ТРУДА: СИСТЕМАТИЧЕСКИЙ ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ ПО РЕГИОНАМ

Аннотация.

Данный систематический обзор литературы представляет всесторонний анализ гендерного разрыва в оплате труда в различных регионах мира, рассматривая ключевые детерминанты, меры политики и применяемые методологии для изучения данного явления. Исследование охватывает развитые, развивающиеся и переходные экономики, уделяя особое внимание Европе, Азии, Северной и Южной

Америке, странам бывшего СССР и Африке. Авторы объединили выводы 73 эмпирических исследований, отобранных из первоначального списка из 1267 источников. Результаты показывают, что, хотя развитые экономики добились прогресса в сокращении разрыва в оплате труда, развивающиеся и переходные экономики продолжают сталкиваться со структурными неравенствами на рынке труда и слабым исполнением политических мер. Будущие исследования должны сосредоточиться на регионально-ориентированных мерах для обеспечения устойчивого сокращения гендерного разрыва в оплате труда.

Ключевые слова: гендерный разрыв в оплате труда, неравенство в заработной плате, региональные различия в заработной плате, систематический обзор литературы.

ГЕНДЕРЛІК ЖАЛАҚЫ АЙЫРМАШЫЛЫҒЫНЫҢ КАРТАСЫ: АЙМАҚТАР БОЙЫНША ЖҮЙЕЛІ ӘДЕБИ ШОЛУ

Андатпа.

Бұл жүйелі әдеби шолу әртүрлі жаһандық аймақтардағы гендерлік жалақы айырмашылығын жан-жақты зерттеп, оның негізгі детерминанттарын, саясаттық шараларын және қолданылатын әдістемелерін талдайды. Зерттеу дамыған, дамушы және өтпелі экономикаларды қамтиды, атап айтқанда Еуропа, Азия, Солтүстік және Оңтүстік Америка, бұрынғы КСРО елдері және Африкаға ерекше назар аударылады. Авторлар 1267 дереккөзден бастапқы түрде таңдалған 73 эмпирикалық зерттеудің нәтижелерін біріктірді. Нәтижелер көрсеткендей, дамыған экономикалар жалақы теңсіздігін азайтуда ілгерілеушілікке қол жеткізгенімен, дамушы және өтпелі экономикалар еңбек нарығындағы құрылымдық теңсіздіктер мен саясатты әлсіз іске асыру мәселелеріне әлі де тап болуда. Болашақ зерттеулер гендерлік жалақы айырмашылығын тұрақты түрде қысқарту үшін өңірге бағытталған араласуларға назар аударуы тиіс.

Түйінді сөздер: гендерлік жалақы айырмашылығы, жалақы теңсіздігі, аймақтық жалақы айырмашылықтары, жүйелі әдеби шолу.

Information about authors:

Irina Kovaleva – **corresponding author**, PhD Student, Assistant at the Dean's Office of the College of Social Sciences, KIMEP University, Department of Economics, Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan

E-mail: i.kovaleva@kimep.kz

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3636-6093>

Информация об авторах:

Ирина Ковалева – докторант, ассистент деканата колледжа социальных наук, Университет КИМЭП, экономический факультет, г. Алматы, Республика Казахстан

E-mail: i.kovaleva@kimep.kz

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3636-6093>

Авторлар туралы ақпарат:

Ирина Ковалева – PhD докторанты, әлеуметтік ғылымдар колледжінің деканатының ассистенті, КИМЭП университеті, экономика кафедрасы, Алматы, Қазақстан Республикасы

E-mail: i.kovaleva@kimep.kz

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3636-6093>